

Studies on the Influence of Some Supporting Electrolytes on the Diffusion Current and Half-wave Potential of the Reducible Ions. Part I. Polarographic Studies

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Variations in the diffusion current (i_d) and half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) have been polarographically studied on the reducible Cd^{2+} ions at different concentrations of KCl, KNO_3 , NaCl, and K_2SO_4 as the supporting electrolytes. Apart from the prevailing view in favour of ionic strength, complex formation, viscosity, etc. to explain the variations in i_d , the roles of the interfacial tension and liquid-junction potential have been critically discussed as additional factors. Since experimental results show that the Ilkovic equation is dependent on several other factors due to the nature of the environment, it has been suggested that each system should be considered as a specific one to probe into the parameters affecting the values of i_d and $E_{1/2}$ and to arrive at a more convincing conclusion.

Recently much interest has been shown to the study of the influence of the parameters of the Ilkovic equation:

$$i_d = 607nD^{1/2}Cm^{3/2}t^{1/2}$$

which governs the current-voltage relationship in polarography. The observations on the influence of supporting electrolytes on diffusion current are rather conflicting; more extensive investigations seem necessary to explain the little variations in i_d or $E_{1/2}$, studied by polarograms.

Lingane and Kolthoff¹ attributed the variations in the limiting currents of some reducible ions by foreign electrolytes to the changes in the effective diffusion coefficient of the reducible ions. Lingane² observed that the increase in $E_{1/2}$ of Tl^+ , Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} at higher concentrations of KCl and KNO_3 was due to the decrease in the value of the activity coefficient of the reducible ion. Donald *et al.*³ stressed the influence of the ionic strength and character of ionic environment on the variations of $E_{1/2}$, observed in different concentrations of supporting electrolytes. Valeck⁴ observed that $E_{1/2}$ of Tl^+ and Pb^{2+} was linear with $\sqrt{\mu}$, where μ was the ionic strength. $E_{1/2}$ was influenced differently by different anions and hence some more factors than the ionic strength and activity coefficient were responsible for the variations. Micka⁵ observed that apart from ionic strength, the rate of mercury flow also influenced the values of $E_{1/2}$ of Tl^+ and Zn^{2+} ions.

1. *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 61, 1045.

2. *Ibid.*, 1930, 61, 2099.

3. *Ibid.*, 1950, 72, 3918.

4. *Chem. Listy*, 1954, 48, 1474.

5. *Ibid.* 1956, 50, 203.

Recently Mukherjee and Chakravarti⁶ studied the influence of supporting electrolytes on $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and i_d of Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Co^{2+} ions and suggested that (i) viscosity, (ii) complex-formation, (iii) ionic strength, (iv) interionic attraction, and (v) hydrogen over-voltage were the probable factors to influence the values of half-wave potentials and diffusion currents.

In view of the conflicting position of the multiparametric influence of concentration of supporting electrolytes, it was deemed necessary to perform some simple experiments on the reducible Cd^{2+} ions in presence of different concentrations of a few supporting electrolytes (KCl, KNO_3 , K_2SO_4 , and NaCl) and critically examine our observations in the light of some other factors such as interfacial tension and liquid-junction potential which may affect the validity of the Ilkovic equation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Current-voltage measurements were made with Lange's polarometer in conjunction with a multiflex galvanometer. The conventional 'H' type of cell was employed with the solution to be examined in one limb and saturated calomel electrode in the other. The two limbs of the 'H' cell were separated by glass wool and an agar plug saturated with KCl⁷. Chemicals of B. D. H. and E. Merck were used and the drop time was maintained at 3 seconds per drop. The solution was deoxygenated by bubbling nitrogen gas after passing it through alkaline pyrogallol for about 15 minutes. Gelatin of concentration 0.02% was used as maximum suppressor. All current measurements were of apparent maximum current, taken just as the drop fell. i_d and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ are respectively expressed in the tables in μA and volt.

TABLE I

Cd^{2+} as the reducing ion in $CdCl_2$ solution.

Conc.	KCl		KNO_3		NaCl		K_2SO_4	
	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$
M/2	9.170	0.630	7.700	0.595	0.360	0.620	..	..
M/4	..	..	..	..	..	..	8.98	0.615
M/10	8.900	0.620	7.700	0.595	8.990	0.610	8.97	0.610
M/25	8.550	0.605	7.710	0.600	8.090	0.595	8.55	0.615
M/100	7.900	0.604	7.710	0.595	8.810	0.595	8.55	0.620

$$i_d(\text{NaCl}) > i_d(\text{KCl}) > i_d(\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4) > i_d(\text{KNO}_3).$$

TABLE II

Cd^{2+} as the reducing ion in $Cd(NO_3)_2$ solution.

Conc.	KCl		KNO_3		NaCl		K_2SO_4	
	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$
M/2	8.905	0.635	8.550	0.595	8.550	0.635	..	..
M/4	..	..	..	..	..	..	7.71	0.625
M/10	8.550	0.615	8.550	0.595	8.360	0.630	7.87	0.610
M/25	8.090	0.615	8.555	0.595	8.170	0.610	7.87	0.605
M/100	7.900	0.610	..	..	8.160	0.610	8.05	0.605

$$i_d(\text{KCl}) > i_d(\text{NaCl}) > i_d(\text{KNO}_3) > i_d(\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4).$$

6. *This Journal*, 1961, 38, 995; 1962, 39, 149.

7. Meltes, "Polarographic Techniques", pp. 21, 52, 1955.

TABLE III

Supporting electrolyte	C_2/C_1	$E = \frac{2u}{u+v} \frac{RT}{N} \cdot \log \frac{C_2}{C_1}$	$E = \frac{2v}{u+v} \frac{RT}{N} \cdot \log \frac{C_2}{C_1}$	Ratio of EMF. (KCl: KNO ₃ : K ₂ SO ₄ : NaCl).
		for faster cation.	for faster anion.	
KCl	50	..	0.1008	0.1008 : 0.1012
KNO ₃	50	0.1032	..	0.0850 : 0.1202
K ₂ SO ₄	25	..	0.0850	
NaCl	50	..	0.1202	

DISCUSSION

The orders of variations in i_d or $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ for the reducible CdCl₂ and Cd(NO₃)₂ with KCl, KNO₃, NaCl, and K₂SO₄ as supporting electrolytes (Tables I and II) apparently suggest that i_d and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ are influenced by the anions of the reducible substances as well as of the supporting electrolytes. Our results are in agreement with those of Mukherjee and Chakravarti⁸. Such observations are suggestive of the fact that each reducible system behaves in a specific manner at different concentrations of the supporting electrolyte and the nature of ionic environments appreciably influences validity of the Ilkovic equation.

To ensure the correspondence to the Ilkovic equation, it is necessary that the polarographic wave should be adequately diffusion-controlled. The basis of the simple and frequently used method for ascertaining the diffusion-controlled heights of the wave is that $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ (and hence, i_d) should be proportional to $\sqrt{P}$, where P is the effective pressure⁷ of mercury. The influence of the capillary factors on the value of m , as derived from Poiseuille's equation, leads to the result that m is directly proportional to the net pressure (P) on the mercury drop; at the same time ' t ' is inversely proportional to this pressure from which $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ becomes proportional to $\sqrt{P}$. Hence i_d is also proportional to $\sqrt{P}$, when the height of the wave is diffusion-controlled. The effective pressure (P) of mercury is represented as h_{eff} , which, according to the Poiseuille equation, is equal to

$$h_{\text{eff}} = \frac{h_{\text{soln.}} d_{\text{soln.}}}{13.5} - \frac{3.1}{m^{1/3} t^{1/3}}$$

where h_{Hg} and $h_{\text{soln.}}$ are the heights of the mercury columns and of the solution above the tip of the capillary, $d_{\text{soln.}}$ is the density of the solution, and $3.1/(m^{1/3} t^{1/3})$ gives the back pressure due to interfacial tension at the drop surface. It follows that for the diffusion-controlled wave $i_d \propto h^{1/2}$ eff. or $i_d/h_{\text{eff}}^{1/2}$ should be a constant over a wide range of mercury pressure within the limit of experimental errors. If not, "the current must be partially or wholly governed by the rate of some processes other than diffusion to the electrode surface".

Since ' t ' is closely proportional to the interfacial tension, it should be considerably influenced by changing the supporting electrolyte or by adding a maximum suppressor. Since adsorption is connected with the interfacial tension, the current may be influenced by this effect also.

M. Lewis⁸ and Patrick⁹ observed that the interfacial tension of the mercury surface was lowered with increasing concentrations of the mercurous nitrate, salicylic acid,

8. *Phil. Mag.*, 1908, 15, 404; 1909, 17, 466.

9. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, 86, 645.

picric acid, etc., according to the Gibbs adsorption equation. From this, it can be visualised that the potential of the dropping mercury electrode may vary with the nature and the concentration of the supporting electrolytes due to adsorption of ions, resulting in the variations of i_d .

The effect of liquid-junction potential may not be negligible. In Table III some calculated values of E. M. F. have been shown by assuming that the appropriate concentration cells have been set up to maintain the ratio of $C_1/C_2=50$. It will be seen that liquid potentials are in the ratio of $E_{KCl} : E_{KNO_3} : E_{K_2SO_4} : E_{NaCl}$ as 0.1008: 0.1032: 0.085: 0.12. The junction potential of K_2SO_4 concentration cell is minimum, whereas that of NaCl is maximum. This order of variations is fairly supported by the values of i_d for $CdCl_2$ in Table I, but not those of Table II for $Cd(NO_3)_2$. From this it may be argued that liquid-junction potential may be able to influence the changes in i_d or E_j , but that may be overcome by other factors also. Such observations evidently suggest that the role of supporting electrolyte is a complicated phenomenon which may vary from system to system. Consequently, each system should be regarded as a specific one and all parameters should be thoroughly examined to determine which of the factors are predominantly responsible for the variation in the diffusion current. The possibility of formation of complexes and the influence of the ionic strength, which have been frequently advocated to explain the variations, are undoubtedly important, but the available results show that these are not adequate to explain the variations in i_d and E_j for all cases. Further work is in progress.